

Spectrophotometric Studies of 8-(*p*-Tolylsulphona-mido)-Quinoline Metal Chelates in Some Water-Miscible Organic Solvents

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8-(*p*-Tolylsulphona-mido)-quinoline has been found by us¹ to form insoluble chelates with many cations. In the present communication we have studied spectrophotometrically the chelates formed by Cu (II), Zn (II), Cd (II), Ni (II), Pb (II) and UO₂ (II) with 8-(*p*-tolylsulphona-mido)-quinoline in two water-miscible organic solvent systems, dimethylformamide as one and a mixture of equal volumes of *n*-propyl alcohol and 1, 4-dioxane as the other with the hope that these reactions might be suitable for their volumetric estimation by the photometric titration technique.

Experimental and Discussion

Preliminary investigations were made in each of the two solvents to establish the correct wave length, pH range, concentrations of the reagent and metallic ions and other suitable conditions for complete reaction. A wave length of 420 m μ was found suitable for all copper determinations. A pH range of 5.0-7.0 was found to give a constant maximum absorbance at 420 m μ . Reagent concentration and mole ratio was determined by plotting the absorbances of solutions containing 0.04M copper and reagent in molar ratio 1 : 0.2 to 1 : 5 at 420 m μ . The results indicated the ratio of reagent to copper for constant maximum absorbance as 2 : 1. Lambert Beer's Law was obeyed in the concentration range of 0.2 ppm to 8 ppm of copper at 420 m μ . The nature of the titration curves for copper in dimethylformamide and in dioxane + *n*-propyl alcohol was essentially the same.

The titration curves for Zn (II) were very similar to those for copper with these solvents. The equilibrium near the equivalence point is less favourable for zinc than for copper titrations. To obtain an end point comparable with copper it was necessary to work with zinc concentrations about 10 times those for copper.

From the location of the end point for the titrations and the amount of copper or zinc present, it was found that 8-(*p*-tolylsulphona-mido)-quinoline was reacting with these metal ions in the ratio of 2 : 1.

Cadmium may be titrated spectrophotometrically in dimethylformamide but with less satisfactory results than copper or zinc. The end point at the 2 : 1 ratio of the reagent to cadmium could be reproduced to $\pm 1\%$. The continued rise of the titration curve past the end point, though at a lesser inclination is probably due to the further addition of the reagent to cadmium complex. In dioxane + *n*-propyl alcohol the end point is not reproducible because of the slow precipitation of the cadmium salt, causing a turbid solution.

Photometric titrations of nickel did not indicate breaks in the curve suitable for analytical determinations. The slope of the curve at a molar ratio of two reagents to one nickel began to increase rather than decrease as in the case of copper and zinc. This may be taken as evidence of the reaction of the reagent with nickel at a molar ratio greater than 2 : 1. Approaching a 3 : 1 ratio the slope of the curve decreased but with considerable curvature.

Solutions of Pb (II) and UO₂ (II) in dioxane + *n*-propyl alcohol could not give any detectable break in the curve at a 2 : 1 molar ratio of the reagent to cation. The system followed Beer's Law relationship until some what past a 1 : 1 ratio of the reagent to cation, when the slope increased and continued beyond the 2 : 1 equivalence point. From the consideration of the results with nickel and cadmium it is reasonable to conclude that a third molecule of the reagent was interfering with these cations.

The results indicated that photometric titrations in water miscible organic solvents, in general, are comparable in accuracy and sensitivity with titrations in water, but are not so versatile.

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Reference

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Potentiometric Assay of Micromole Quantities of Methylene-blue using Hexanitrate Ammonium Cerate (IV)*

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MORRAW¹ proposed an iodometric method for the determination of methylene blue and claimed that one molecule of methylene blue absorbs five atoms of iodine in the presence of acetic acid, while others^{2, 3, 4} claimed that one molecule of methylene blue absorbs 6 atoms of iodine in the presence of sodium acetate. But Holmes⁵ stated that the amount of iodine taken up by methylene blue is proportional to the concentration of excess iodine present. Ferrey⁶, proposed an indirect method for the determination of methylene blue by precipitating it with excess dichromate, the excess being estimated iodometrically. Suprun⁷ determined methylene-blue iodo chlorometrically in acid as well as in alkaline medium. Picric acid was used as a reagent for volumetric⁸ and gravimetric⁹ determination of methylene blue. Several other gravimetric determinations of

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